

COMPARISON OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK VERBS: FEATURES AND SIMILARITIES

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Abstract:

This article is dedicated to a comparison of verbs in the Russian and Uzbek languages, focusing on their grammatical categories, types, tense forms, and conjugation features. The article also emphasizes that the Uzbek infinitive has a unified ending -mok, in contrast to the more varied endings in Russian. The study highlights both similarities and differences between the verbal systems of the two languages, which can be useful when teaching Russian to Uzbek speakers and vice versa.

Keywords: comparison, verb, grammatical category, tense, type of verb, infinitive, conjugation.

Introduction

The verb is one of the key parts of speech in any language, as it expresses an action, state, or process. Comparing verbs in Russian and Uzbek is of interest from the perspective of typological differences and similarities. Russian belongs to the Slavic group of the Indo-European family [*Modern Russian Language: Textbook* / Edited by N.S. Valgina. - 6th ed., revised and supplemented. Moscow: Logos, 2002. - 52], while Uzbek belongs to the Turkic language family. Despite belonging to different language families, there are both significant differences and certain points of intersection between their verbal systems. [*Khoziev A. Fi'l (Verb)*. - Tashkent: Fan, 1973.] This article discusses the main features of the verbal systems in the Russian and Uzbek languages.

General Characteristics of Verbs in Russian and Uzbek

1. Grammatical Categories of Verbs

In Russian, verbs are characterized by categories of tense, aspect, voice, person, number, and mood. The Uzbek language also has categories of tense, mood, number, and person. [*Khoziev A. Fi'l (Verb)*. - Tashkent: Fan, 1973.] However, the aspect of verbs in Uzbek is expressed less explicitly and is often conveyed through context or additional grammatical means. Thus, while both languages

have tense and personal categories, their aspect systems and methods of expressing tense differ significantly.

Aspect of the Verb

In Russian, the aspect category is expressed morphologically: verbs are either perfective or imperfective. [*Modern Russian Language* / Edited by V.A. Beloshapkova. Moscow: Higher School, 1989.] For example, "читать" (imperfective) and "прочитать" (perfective) differ both in form and meaning. In Uzbek, there is no clear distinction between perfective and imperfective aspects. The aspect is mostly determined by context or auxiliary forms. For instance, "оқиш" (to read) does not differentiate between perfectiveness or imperfectiveness, but the context can clarify whether the reading is a process or a completed action.

2. Tense Forms

In Russian, there are traditionally three tenses: past, present, and future. The future tense can be either simple or compound, depending on the aspect. In Uzbek, there are also past, present, and future tenses, but there are additional specific forms such as "past hypothetical" and "future hypothetical," which express additional nuances of time. For example, "келди" means "he/she came," "келади" means "he/she comes/will come," and "келар" can indicate the probability that someone will come.

3. Infinitive

In Russian, infinitives typically end in -ть or -ти (e.g., "петь," "идти"). In Uzbek, the infinitive always ends in -моқ (e.g., "ўқимоқ" – to read, "келмоқ" – to come). This gives the Uzbek infinitive greater uniformity compared to the Russian one.

4. Verb Conjugation

In Russian, verbs are divided into two main conjugations, each with its own distinctive endings depending on person and number. In Uzbek, verbs are conjugated by adding personal suffixes to the verb stem. For example, "мен ўқийман" (I read), "сен ўқийсан" (you read), "у ўқийди" (he/she reads).

Similarities Between Russian and Uzbek Verbs

1. Usage of Verbs in a Sentence

In both languages, verbs function as predicates, expressing the main action in a sentence. This fundamental similarity makes it possible to compare their verbal systems.

2. Personal Forms

In both Russian and Uzbek, verbs change according to person and number. For example:

Russian: "я читаю," "ты читаешь," "он читает."

Uzbek: "мен ўқийман," "сен ўқийсан," "у ўқийди."

This allows for the expression of actions performed by different subjects.

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3. Tense Category

Both languages have a tense category that includes past, present, and future tenses. Despite differences in the structure of tense forms, both languages have means of expressing the time of an action, allowing for the conveyance of temporal relations between events.

Differences Between Russian and Uzbek Verbs

1. Absence of Aspect Category in Uzbek

In Uzbek, there is no clear distinction between perfective and imperfective aspect, making direct translation of Russian verbs challenging. For example, the Russian verbs "писать" (to write) and "написать" (to write, perfective) can both be translated as "ёзмок" (to write), and the context will determine whether the action is completed.

2. Affixation in Uzbek

Uzbek actively uses affixes to form verb tenses, which is a characteristic feature of Turkic languages. For example, to form the future tense, an affix "-ади" is added to the verb stem (e.g., "келади" – "he/she will come"). In Russian, the future tense is often formed with auxiliary verbs or by using different forms of perfective verbs. [http://socialtranslation.ru/maqola.php?article_id=395]

3. Complex Tense Forms in Uzbek

Uzbek has more tense forms than Russian. This allows for more precise expression of temporal nuances, such as the completion of an action or probability. For example, in Uzbek, there is the form "келган эди" ("he/she had come") which expresses a more complex temporal relationship than its Russian counterpart.

4. Infinitive in Uzbek

The Uzbek infinitive always ends in -мок, making it less varied compared to the Russian infinitive, which can have different endings (e.g., -ть, -ти).

Examples of Verb Comparisons

Russian: "пить" – Uzbek: "ичмок"

Russian: "читать" – Uzbek: "ўқимок"

Russian: "делать" – Uzbek: "қилиш"

Russian: "пойти" – Uzbek: "кетмок"

Conclusion

The comparison of Russian and Uzbek verbs shows how different linguistic systems express similar grammatical and semantic categories. Despite differences in structure and approaches to forming verb forms, both languages effectively convey actions, states, or processes. This research has practical value, especially in the context of teaching Russian to Uzbek speakers and vice versa. Understanding the features of the verbal systems can improve translation skills and facilitate a deeper mastery of both languages.

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